

Magnetoelastic softening in cold-sprayed polycrystalline nickel studied by resonant ultrasound spectroscopy

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INTRODUCTION

Cold spray is a cost-efficient and rapid additive manufacturing method for deposition of materials from feedstock powders. The powder particles are accelerated to supersonic velocities by a pressurized gas jet, and they undergo severe plastic deformation upon their impact onto the substrate or the preceding sprayed layers. Extreme-rate viscoplastic deformation ultimately leads to the formation of a very strong bond between the particles [1]. Hence, the final deposits exhibit a unique, highly deformed microstructure and significant residual compressive stress. These stresses are not commonly assessed using ultrasonic methods, since the elasto-acoustic constants in metals are relatively low, making it difficult to distinguish the effects of residual stress on acoustic parameters from those originating from defects. Fortunately, in magnetostrictive ferromagnetic materials, residual stresses affect elasticity through magnetoelastic coupling, leading to an effective softening of the elastic response, also known as the ΔE effect. Hence, the suppression of this anelastic relaxation by residual stresses opens the possibility of examining them using laser-ultrasonics.

MATERIALS, METHODS, AND RESULTS

With contactless resonant ultrasound spectroscopy, we studied three polycrystalline nickel materials – two cold-sprayed deposits and a rolled sheet as a reference – with different levels of plasticity-induced grain refinement and substructuring (documented by EBSD), hence, also of the residual stresses. The evolution of the shear modulus (G) and the internal friction parameter with temperature was monitored during a heating-cooling cycle across the Curie point (T_c), both before and after annealing at 700 °C, see [2] for details. Figure 1 compares the pre-annealing cycle results for a cold-sprayed deposit with a high level of residual stress with those of the rolled sheet used as reference material. In both cases, crossing the Curie point leads to a distinct change in behavior, with apparent nonlinearity and irreversibility in the ferromagnetic region. The convex shape of the curves in this region is most pronounced for the

Figure 1: Difference in shear moduli (G) evolution during temperature cycling above Curie point (T_c) for a) Ni rolled sheet, and b) Ni cold-sprayed deposit with high level of residual stresses.

cooling branch of the cold-sprayed deposit, and it became much more striking for all samples in the same heating-cooling cycle performed after annealing at 700 °C (not present).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The minimum of the G curve in the ferromagnetic region marks the strongest magnetoelastic coupling, which is deeply stress-dependent. For the rolled sheet, the more pronounced non-linearity during cooling indicates that relaxation of internal stresses during the cycle enhances the ΔE effect. In the cold-sprayed sample, no sharp change in the slope of G at T_c is observed during heating, indicating that the ΔE effect is completely suppressed initially; the cooling curve closely resembles the theoretical prediction for polycrystalline nickel with low residual stresses. Hence, our results in [2] document that the presence and intensity of residual stresses, as well as their mitigation through recrystallization, can be efficiently analyzed using laser-ultrasonics in ferromagnetic magnetostrictive materials via the ΔE effect.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financially supported by the Czech Science Foundation [project No. 24-10334S] and by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic in the frame of the 'Ferroc multifunctionalities' project [No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004591], co-funded by the European Union.

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